

Analysis of Consumer Food Purchasing Behavior Using Shopeefood Application in Gunungpati Subdistrict, Semarang City

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study how the influence of discounts, ease of use, and ease of payment in influencing the decision to use the ShopeeFood application in Gunungpati District and its surroundings. The population of this study is all residents who live in Gunungpati Subdistrict and its surroundings. While the research sample is residents of Gunungpati and its surroundings who actively use the ShopeeFood application. The sampling technique used purposive sampling method and obtained 50 respondents. The results of hypothesis testing indicate that all discount variables, ease of use and ease of payment have a significant positive effect on the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. The coefficient of determination test shows that the variables of discounts, ease of use and ease of payment can influence the decision to use the ShopeeFood application by 78.7%. While the remaining 21.3% is influenced by other variables

INTRODUCTION

Information technology has developed very fast in recent years. This is used by producers to sell their products through e-commerce. (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023). Selling goods online is considered capable of increasing sales due to the large number of Android and IOS-based mobile phone users today. In addition, the Marketplace also makes it easy for sellers to develop their products so that they can be marketed online.

Marketplace is a container or place to market products or services electronically that brings together many sellers and buyers to transact with each other online (Opiida, 2023). The highest user marketplace is Shopee, according to a survey from (Similarweb, 2023) Shopee is ranked first with 237 million visitors throughout 2023. Shopee has complete features that make visitors and users able to maximize their desire to shop. In addition, the most daily visitors to Shopee are visitors who use the ShopeeFood feature. This feature provides ample space for merchants to sell food and beverage products online that can be widely accessed by Shopee users. The ShopeeFood feature can be accessed by visitors from all regions of Indonesia.

(Fairuz Salsabila, 2023) explains that ShopeeFood makes it easy for users to order food and beverages instantly without having to leave the house. The number of visitors to ShopeeFood is increasing every day, as is the number of sellers using ShopeeFood to sell their food and beverage products. ShopeeFood users get attractive promos every day, which makes them choose to shop at ShopeeFood (Oktaviano, 2023). With so many promos, consumers are increasingly interested in using ShopeeFood to meet their needs, especially for consumers who are very busy. Research by (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Oktaviano, 2023), (Naufal, 2023), (Putra, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022) explains that there are strong enough influences on consumer behavior on decisions to use the ShopeeFood application. These factors include discounts, ease of use and ease of payment.

(Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022) explain that discounts are able to lure consumer decisions to buy and use online buying and selling applications. Research by (Naufal, 2023), (Putra, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022) states that the ShopeeFood application is very easy to use and makes consumers interested in using it. In addition, many consumers use ShopeeFood because the payment is very easy. This has been researched by (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), (Sundari, 2023), and (Febrianti, 2023) who found that ease of payment can increase the decision to use an application.

This study tries to formulate that consumer behavior in using the ShopeeFood application. This is due to the increasing number of users of the Shopee application as they take advantage of the ShopeeFood program to order food. The influencing factors are believed to be due to discounts, ease of use and ease of payment

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Behavior

(Kotler & Keller, 2017) Consumer behavior is the study of individuals and groups in choosing goods, making purchase decisions, and using goods or services to meet needs in order to achieve satisfaction with the product or service. As technology evolves, consumers are becoming more intelligent in their choices. (Raymond Mcleod, 2007) Information technology is one of the tools used by managers to manage the changes that occur. (Kotler & Keller, 2017) explains that usage decisions are one of the shapers of consumer behavior where the desire to choose, buy, use and decide to be able to satisfy them. With the times, consumers use information technology a lot to be able to satisfy their needs and even the frequency of use reaches almost every day.

Hypothesis Formulation and Development

1. The Effect of Discounts on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

Discounts in shopping are indeed something that consumers look for and look forward to. Each manufacturer offers different discounts depending on the ability and type of goods sold. In online sales in the marketplace, many offer various discounts that make consumers want to use the marketplace application to get discounts. In the ShopeeFood application, the discounts offered are very diverse and can attract consumers to use the ShopeeFood application to meet their needs. This is stated in previous research by (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022), which explains that discounts can lure consumers' decisions to buy and use online buying and selling applications. Based on previous statements and research, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely

H1 : Discounts have a significant positive effect on the decision to use the ShopeeFood application.

2. The Effect of Ease of Use on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

Information technology in recent years is considered to be able to provide convenience in satisfying consumer needs. This is because the application on the mobile phone is very easy to use. Consumers simply order from home and the goods arrive at home in a short time. This convenience can encourage consumers to decide to use the ShopeeFood application. Research by (Naufal, 2023), (Putra, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022) states that the ShopeeFood application is very easy to use and makes consumers interested in using it. Based on the previous statements and research, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely

H2: Ease of use has a significant positive effect on the decision to use the ShopeeFood application.

3. The Impact of Ease of Payment on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

ShopeeFood provides convenience of payment when ordering food or beverages. This payment can be done through cash on delivery (COD) and through ShopeePay. This convenience makes consumers want to use the ShopeeFood application. Research by (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), (Sundari, 2023), and (Febrianti, 2023) which resulted in findings that ease

of payment can increase decisions to use an application. Based on previous statements and research, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely

H3 : Ease of payment has a significant positive effect on the decision to use the ShopeeFood application.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This type of research is an explanatory research (Sugiyono, 2020). The population in this study are all residents who live in Gunungpati district and its surroundings, which are unlimited in number. The sample used in the study were residents of Gunungpati and its surroundings who actively used the ShopeeFood application, and was calculated using non-probability sampling with the following conditions:

- 1). Local residents of Gunungpati district;
- 2). Owning the Shopee application and actively using Shopee;
- 3). Placing orders through ShopeeFood more than 20 times in one month.

Through these conditions, a sample of 50 respondents was obtained. The data collection method used questionnaires and interviews with the respondents. The data analysis method uses the data instrument test and the model feasibility test using the SPSS version 25 program.

RESULTS

Respondent Profile

Based on the data collected and processed using SPSS with a sample of 50 respondents. The gender of male respondents in this study was 10 people or 20%, while the female gender was 40 people or 80%. The majority of respondents in the study had an age range of 20-29 years or as many as 35 people and the least in the age range of 50-59 years or as many as 3 people. While the majority of the research respondents have an undergraduate education as many as 25 people or 50%, the remaining 50% consist of high school/vocational school and D3 education.

Data Analysis

Data Instrument Test

Based on the results of the processed data, the validity test in this study shows that all the r counts on each question / item in all variables are greater than the r table = 0.146. These results can indicate that the indicators of each variable in the study can be declared valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test shows that all variables have an alpha coefficient greater than 0.70, so it can be said that the variables used in the study are declared reliable.

Model Feasibility Test

The model feasibility test includes the F test, the coefficient of determination test, and the hypothesis test. The results of data processing can be presented as follows:

Table 1. Model Feasibility Test

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1874.297	3	624.766	166.315	.000 ^a
	Residual	492.103	50	3.757		
	Total	2366.400	47			

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2023

Based on the above table, it can be concluded that all variables (discounts, ease of use and ease of payment) together (simultaneously) have a significant positive effect on the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. This can be seen from the value of the F-table (166.315), which is greater than the F-count (2.80). in addition, the test of the coefficient of determination resulted in the finding of an adjusted R2 value of 0.787. this can be interpreted as meaning that the variables discounts, ease of use and ease of payment are able to influence the decision to use the ShopeeFood application by 78.7%. while the remaining 21.3% is influenced by the variable use of the ShopeeFood application. While the remaining 21.3% are influenced by other variables.

Table 2. Standardized Coefficients

Model		Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)		1.067	.288
	Discounts (X1)	.394	6.395	.000
	Ease of use (X2)	.373	6.349	.000
	Ease of payment (X3)	.228	3.530	.001

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2023

- 1). The test results of the discount variable on usage decisions show the value of $t \text{ count} = 6.395 > t \text{ table} = 1.656$, with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be said that the provision of daily discounts is able to increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. (H1 accepted)
- 2). The results of testing the ease of use variable on usage decisions show the value of $t \text{ count} = 6.349 > t \text{ table} = 1.656$, with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be said that the ease of use of ShopeeFood application is able to increase the usage decisions. (H2 accepted)
- 3). The results of testing the ease of payment variable on usage decisions show the value of $t \text{ count} = 3.530 > t \text{ table} = 1.656$, with a significance of $0.001 < 0.05$. Therefore, it can be said that the ease of payment on ShopeeFood can increase usage decisions. (H3 accepted)

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Discounts on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

Based on the test results, it can be said that the discount variable has a significant positive effect on usage decisions. Thus, it can be said that offering daily discounts can increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. This is consistent with the results of research by (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022), which explain that discounts are able to lure consumer decisions to buy and use online buying and selling applications. Discounts in ShopeeFood are very diverse and must be every day. This makes consumers very interested and decide to use the ShopeeFood application. In addition, the discounts offered can also be added to payments made with Shopee Coins and free shipping vouchers, which makes ShopeeFood users even more eager to continue using and shopping with ShopeeFood. Thus, it can be said that the hypothesis formulated is accepted.

The Effect of Usability on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

Based on the test results, it can be said that the variable ease of use has a significant positive effect on the decision to use the application. Thus, it can be said that the ease of use of the ShopeeFood application is able to increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. This is consistent with the findings of (Naufal, 2023), (Putra, 2023), and (Al-Farabi, 2022), which state that the ShopeeFood application is very easy to use and makes consumers interested in using it. Many consumers state that the ShopeeFood application is very easy to use. Consumers simply install the application on their mobile phone and create an account. Later, it is directly integrated into ShopeeFood itself. Ordering is also very easy, consumers can see the ad that is displayed, then just click according to the existing procedures and directly there will be ShopeeFood drivers who will contact consumers either via chat or telephone. Later, our order will be delivered to the place where the consumer is located. Thus, it can be said that the hypothesis formulated is accepted.

The Effect of Ease of Payment on the Decision to Use the ShopeeFood Application

Based on the test results, the Ease of Payment variable has a significant positive effect on the usage decision. Thus, it can be said that ease of payment is able to increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application. This is consistent with the research of (Fairuz Salsabila, 2023), (Nadia Destovia, 2023), (Sundari, 2023), and (Febrianti, 2023), who found that ease of payment can increase the decision to use an application. Consumers who have the Shopee application say that transactions on ShopeeFood are very easy. Consumers can top up their ShopeePay balance through ATM transfers, m-banking or top up at outlets that accept ShopeePay. Later, when ordering from ShopeeFood, consumers can pay through ShopeePay or Cash On Delivery (COD). Consumers who have no funds in their ShopeePay can pay when the ShopeeFood courier arrives at their destination. Thus, it can be said that the hypothesis formulated is accepted

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1). The results of testing hypothesis 1 (H1) state that discounts have a significant positive effect, so it can be interpreted that the more frequent discounts at ShopeeFood will increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application.
- 2). The results of testing hypothesis 2 (H2) state that ease of use has a positive effect on usage decisions, so it can be interpreted that the easier it is to use the ShopeeFood application, it will increase usage decisions.
- 3). The results of testing hypothesis 3 (H3) state that ease of payment has a significant positive effect on usage decisions. So it can be interpreted that the easier it is to pay, the more it can increase the decision to use the ShopeeFood application.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Analysis of Consumer Food Purchasing Behavior Using ShopeeFood Application in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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